

Report on the EOSC Winter School

2025

20–23 January 2025
Seville, Spain

Report on the EOSC Winter School 2025

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Terminology

Table 1: Acronyms used in the 2025 EOSC Winter School Report

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
CAT	Compliance Assessment Toolkit
CDIF	Cross-domain Interoperability Framework
CEDS	Common European Data Spaces
DG CNECT	European Commission Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology
DG RTD	European Commission Directorate-General for Research & Innovation
DSSC	Data Spaces Support Center
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-A	EOSC Association
EOSC IF	EOSC Interoperability Framework
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
HE	Horizon Europe
HE EOSC-related projects	Horizon Europe INFRAEOSC and related projects supporting EOSC
INFRAEOSC projects	Destination INFRAEOSC projects within the EU's research and innovation funding programme
KER	Key exploitable result
MAR	EOSC Partnership Multi-annual Roadmap
Macro-Roadmap	The Macro-Roadmap for the implementation of EOSC - a visual mapping of the results of EU projects developing EOSC and the in-kind contributions of EOSC Association member organisations
OAEG	Opportunity Area Expert Group
OAEG1	Opportunity Area Expert Group 1 - Persistent Identifiers
OAEG2	Opportunity Area Expert Group 2 - Metadata, Ontologies and Interoperability
OAEG3	Opportunity Area Expert Group 3 - FAIR Assessment and Alignment
OAEG4	Opportunity Area Expert Group 4 - User and Resource Environments
OAEG5	Opportunity Area Expert Group 5 - Skills, Training, Rewards, Recognition and Upscaling
OAEG6	Opportunity Area Expert Group 6 - Open Scholarly Communication
OAEG7	Opportunity Area Expert Group 7 - Research Software
PID	Persistent Identifier
RAG	Retrieval-Augmented Generation
SKG	Scientific Knowledge Graph
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
SP	Strategic Pillar (as defined in the MAR 2026-27)
TF	EOSC-A Task Force
TF1	Technical and Semantic Interoperability Task Force
TF2	FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects Task Force
TF3	Health Data Task Force
TF4	Long-Term Data Retention Task Force
VRE	Virtual Research Environments
WS	Winter School

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Executive Summary

The present document reports on the second EOSC Winter School, organised in Seville (Spain) in early 2025 by the EOSC Association (EOSC-A), with the support and participation of the EOSC Focus project, Horizon Europe (HE) EOSC-related projects, EOSC-A Task Forces, and Opportunity Area Expert Groups (OAEs). Representatives from the European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD), and Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology (DG CONNECT) also participated in the event.

The 2025 EOSC Winter School was conceived to align efforts and strengthen collaboration between key stakeholders from the EOSC community involved in EOSC-related projects, under the motto Convergence towards the EOSC Federation: Encouraging collaborative efforts among stakeholders. The "school" format lends itself as a good environment to streamline results from the projects. This is expected to facilitate the delivery of "one EOSC" that is more than the sum of their individual results.

The content for the discussions was organised around the priorities for the further development of EOSC, identified in four Strategic Pillars of the EOSC Partnership's Multi-Annual Roadmap 2026-2027¹:

- Strategic Pillar 1: Sustaining and enhancing the EOSC Federation
- Strategic Pillar 2: Contributing to the web of FAIR data and the uptake of AI
- Strategic Pillar 3: Ensuring research security and sovereignty
- Strategic Pillar 4: Linking with other Common European Data Spaces and beyond

The priorities of the Strategic Pillars were used to tailor the discussions at three levels (European, national, and institutional) to devise recommendations and activities that could be acted upon ensuring a successful implementation of EOSC. Discussions were organised in seven topic-centred groups with participants from OAEs and EOSC-A Task Forces:

1. Persistent Identifiers (PIDs)
2. Interoperability in EOSC
3. FAIR Assessment and Data Objects
4. User and Resource Environments: Trusted VREs and EOSC Federation Model
5. Skills & Engagement
6. Integrating Open Scholarly Communication within EOSC
7. Research Software

The outcome of the discussions, together with reflections on the progress made since the 2024 EOSC Winter School and the next steps, were presented in plenary meetings.

This report focuses on the recommendations identified in seven topic-centred groups, which form the main result of the Winter School and are foreseen to inform the work plans for the Opportunity Area Expert Groups. Together with the activities and outcomes suggested, they demonstrate the continuous commitment of the EOSC community to advancing on the shared

¹ Section 8.1-8.4 (pages 144-147) of the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) 1.3. https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/20241031_SRIA_1.3_final_Annex.pdf

objectives. A description of the preparation of the EOSC Winter School, and summaries of the discussions, are included as well as background material.

A third EOSC Winter School, building on the lessons learned and featuring an updated methodology, is planned for early 2026 with the support of the EOSC Gravity project, which will succeed EOSC Focus in June 2025.

1. Introduction: Converging towards the Federation

1.1 Setting the scene

Since the first EOSC Winter School in January 2024², the development of EOSC has advanced to a new stage. The EOSC EU Node was launched in October 2024, and the first iteration of the EOSC Federation encompassing the first group of EOSC Nodes is under preparation³. Meanwhile, the Tripartite Governance of the EOSC Partnership has formed the Tripartite Group to steer the community development of the EOSC Federation. The Tripartite Group has endorsed the EOSC Association to lead the community-wide co-creation of the EOSC Federation Handbook⁴, which will become the reference document for the operation of the EOSC Federation. A second edition of the EOSC Winter School was thus deemed a good opportunity to keep the momentum and ensure good alignment among HE EOSC-related projects. The “school” (i.e., three-day workshop) format is now well established among project representatives, EOSC-A Task Forces, and Opportunity Area Expert Group members.

The topic of the 2025 EOSC Winter School, *Convergence towards the EOSC Federation: Encouraging collaborative efforts among stakeholders*, was chosen to reflect the present status of EOSC, between a vision that has grown owing to significant investment by the EC and EU Member States and Associated Countries, and the emerging Federation. The event took place at a time where all efforts must converge in order to create a coherent system of systems—the EOSC Federation.

1.2 Methodology

The programme of the Winter School revolved around the “Strategic Pillars” outlined in the EOSC Multi-Annual Roadmap (MAR) priorities for 2026 and 2027:⁵

- Strategic Pillar 1: Sustaining and enhancing the EOSC Federation
- Strategic Pillar 2: Contributing to the web of FAIR data and the uptake of AI
- Strategic Pillar 3: Ensuring research security and sovereignty
- Strategic Pillar 4: Linking with other Common European Data Spaces and beyond

This strategic view has been combined with the perspectives and groundwork laid by volunteers in the seven Opportunity Area Expert Groups (OAEs) and four EOSC-A Task Forces (TFs)⁶, which jointly represent the EOSC brain pool.

The breakout sessions discussed the challenges in each of the Strategic Pillars along the following topics:

- the role of PIDs for the sustainability of the EOSC Federation

² For a comprehensive summary of its objectives and outcomes, see the 2024 EOSC Winter School report: <https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/Report-on-the-EOSC-Winter-School-2024.pdf>.

³ <https://eosc.eu/news/2025/02/eoscs-build-up-phase-to-begin-with-march-kick-off/>

⁴ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-federation-handbook/>

⁵ <https://eosc.eu/sria-mar/>. The Strategic Pillars resulted from the consultation carried out by the EOSC Association in the spring of 2024 about the future Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA v3.0). The MAR is an integral part of the SRIA.

⁶ The composition of the Opportunity Area Expert Groups and EOSC-A Task Forces is explained later in the report.

- interoperability across and beyond the Federation
- assessment tools and methods to advance the FAIR principles, and ensure the quality and preservation of (FAIR) Digital Objects across projects and communities
- guidance on technical requirements to join the EOSC Federation to providers of infrastructure, Virtual Research Environments (VREs) and other services, exploring the technical procedures to enrol as a Node from the initial experiences of EOSC Beyond pilots, and gather feedback on the enrolment and onboarding processes
- activities related to skills, engagement and adoption to make Open Science the new normal, as included in the Strategic Pillars
- the integration of Open Scholarly Communication in EOSC that embraces diverse forms of scientific records, supporting the development and sustainability of collaborative scientific infrastructures
- implementing an interoperable, community-driven vision for research software in EOSC

The breakout sessions were free to choose the methodology in the discussions. Each session was followed by a reporting plenary to share the outcomes. The groups were tasked with defining recommendations and further actions by the end of the WS, while also revisiting the medium- and long-term objectives set during the 2024 event. The organisation of the programme and of the breakout sessions was guided by the EOSC-A with the support of the EOSC Focus project.

By addressing the Strategic Pillars individually within each area, this format has facilitated the alignment of ongoing project work with the priority areas defined by the Strategic Pillars, along which the development of EOSC is envisioned. It also provides a valuable opportunity to ensure that the community advances in a coordinated manner towards the shared goal of delivering “one EOSC”.

The rest of the report is organised as follows (not in the chronological order of the programme): Chapter 2 presents the outcomes of the breakout sessions, first as they pertain to the four Strategic Pillars, then in terms of recommendations, desired activities and outcomes. Chapter 3 provides a summary of the opening session of the Winter School, including an overview of the updates delivered by the EC and EOSC-A. Chapter 4 reflects on the closing session, including a brief evaluation of the progress achieved since the 2024 EOSC Winter School. Chapter 5 takes a step back to reflect on the 2025 EOSC Winter School, taking feedback given by participants into account. The annex provides detailed information on the organisation of the event, including the programme development process, the structure and composition of the breakout sessions, as well as an overview of the Winter School participants and their affiliations. It also includes details on the programme sub-committees and EOSC-related projects represented at the Winter School.

1.3 Basic facts & figures

Table 2: Basic Information on the 2025 EOSC Winter School

Topic/Motto	Convergence towards the EOSC Federation: Encouraging collaborative efforts among stakeholders
Organiser	EOSC Association
Support	EOSC Focus project
Venue	Hotel Meliá Lebreros, Seville (Spain)
Date	20-23 January 2025

Attendees	EOSC OAEGs: 113 EOSC-A TFs: 18 EOSC-A Board & Secretariat: 18 EC: 2
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1.4 Opportunity Area Expert Groups and EOSC-A Task Forces

This subsection provides an overview of the [Opportunity Area Expert Groups](#) (OAEGs) and [EOSC-A Task Forces](#) (TFs) that contributed to the seven breakout sessions.

- OAEG1: PIDs
- OAEG2: Metadata, ontologies & interoperability
- OAEG3: FAIR Metric & Assessment
- OAEG4: User & resource environments
- OAEG5: Skills, Training, Rewards, Recognition, and Upscaling
- OAEG6: Open Scholarly Communication
- OAEG7: Research Software
- TF1: Technical and Semantic Interoperability Task Force
- TF2: FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects Task Force
- TF3: Health Data Task Force
- TF4: Long-Term Data Retention Task Force

2 Results of the 2025 EOSC Winter School

2.1 Inputs of the breakout sessions to the Strategic Pillars

In this section, the main outcome of the 2025 EOSC Winter School, i.e. the conclusions reached in the breakout sessions, are presented, ordered according to the four Strategic Pillars. A more detailed account of the discussions held in each breakout session is provided below (section 2.3).

2.1.1 SP1 – Sustaining and enhancing the EOSC Federation

- A federation-wide PID Policy is fundamental to establishing the EOSC Federation and should therefore be owned by an organisation with the necessary authority and mandate within its governance structure. To achieve this in a timely fashion, the PID Policy needs to be considered by the current tripartite governance of the EOSC Partnership.
- PID-related Key exploitable results (KERs) from projects have the potential to support PID implementation in EOSC. They do however need to be better aligned.
- To address the challenges identified in the EOSC Interoperability Framework (including semantic and technical interoperability), discussions focused on identifying approaches to creating a catalogue (“yellow pages”) of existing and emerging solutions as well as defining and describing use cases and connected user stories exposing interoperability in the Federation of EOSC Nodes.
- Regarding the EOSC EU Node, more automation is needed, as well as more credits for doing meaningful research.
- To enhance and support adoption of EOSC, dissemination and raising awareness about the EOSC Federation with all stakeholders is crucial, including appropriate training, as well as support of recognition and reward practices and infrastructure that incentivize adoption of EOSC (OS practices).

2.1.2 SP2 – Contributing to the Web of FAIR Data and the Uptake of AI

- An assessment body is needed for PIDs & Long-Term Data Retention to build a well-grounded Web of FAIR Data and enable the uptake of AI. More generally, the area is in need of a clear governance structure.
- Efficient and precise use of AI for research purposes requires PIDs and scientific knowledge graphs to include classifications, entity recognition, imputed relationships and annotated content.
- There is a need to distinguish between “FAIR for AI” (knowledge graphs, use of semantic artefacts) and “AI for FAIR” (metadata quality assessment using Large Language Models), to discuss what is “FAIR enough” when it comes to AI in research.
- A key question is whether FAIR data are sufficient for training AI models. AI needs qualified data. Assessing or expressing a degree of data quality and its indicators is not the same as FAIR indicators. FAIR is key for transparency, data quality and provenance should be declared as FAIR for trustworthy and reliable reusability. Therefore, the role of FAIR in AI needs to be clarified (quality vs. reproducibility vs. reusability).
- Finally, breakout sessions discussed how to effectively use metadata to describe links between publications, research data, supplementary data, and data availability

statements. Further work is needed to connect the Diamond Discovery Hub to the EOSC EU Node Resource Hub, as well as to ensure semantic interoperability between publications and research data.

- A potential KER for EOSC related to skills & training is a (FAIR) one-stop-shop to find all relevant skills & engagement resources. This would include (an) EOSC Training Catalogue(s), for which the scope and remit still need to be defined.

2.1.3 SP3 – Ensuring research security and sovereignty / SP4 – Linking with other Common European Data Spaces and beyond

- Re-appraisal workflow should point to PID policy and recommendations for data that is deleted, transferred, or updated.
- Definitions and implementations of both EOSC and data spaces are evolving rapidly and fairly independently, creating opportunities to build interoperability solutions and demonstrators.
- Frameworks such as the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF) can be used to break down the interoperability challenge into more manageable components.
- Engagement between EOSC and data spaces is needed before bridging approaches and definition/selection of open standards and APIs can proceed efficiently.
- Software architecture for data spaces could serve as a protocol to connect data spaces.
- A common model for metrics, tests and associated benchmarks across FAIR tools is required.
- There is a need for Data Quality and Provenance models.
- Create an authority for selecting metrics and defining community benchmarks.
- There needs to be a common approach to FAIR across spaces where possible, to ensure transparency of local/specific FAIR criteria where necessary. Moreover, it should engage with the Common European Data Spaces (CEDs), e.g. through the Data Spaces Support Center (DSSC) to seek alignment.
- There is a lack of harmonized metadata in AI models. Responsibility and liability for sensitive data disclosure needs to be defined.
- A harmonised operational (including cybersecurity aspects) and legal framework must be defined to facilitate the secure sharing and governance of, and access to, data and services.
- A dialogue with CEDs and the EU Missions (Ocean, Climate Adaption) must be established to harmonize the “vocabulary” of Long-Term Data Preservation (LTDR) with the “glossary” of the PID Policy.
- More use cases are needed that explore the integration of Data Spaces within the EOSC Federation, to clarify how interoperability with the CEDs is to be achieved.

2.2 Launch of Opportunity Area Expert Group 7 – Research software

The new [Opportunity Area Expert Group for Research Software](#) (OAE7) was launched at the 2025 EOSC WS. The Expert Group aims to promote all aspects of research software, including metadata, quality, preservation, registries, reproducibility, and recognition. Building on prior volunteer work, this expert group is poised to tackle how an Open Science culture for research software can be best fostered, with the goal of promoting software to become a “first-class citizen” in science.

2.3 Recommendations, desired activities and outcomes from breakout sessions

The condensed formulations presented in the previous section provide only a high-level summary of the in-depth discussions held in the breakout sessions. Below, we present the full list of recommendations, desired activities and outcomes identified in each breakout session to ensure all key points are accurately reflected.

2.3.1 Persistent identifiers (PIDs) (OAEG1+TF4)

Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) are fundamental components of the EOSC Federation, as they enable reproducibility, transparency, interoperability, as well as seamless collaboration across nodes, services and data providers. Furthermore, agreed standards and proper PID technologies also allow better support of AI for research purposes, when it comes to more precise results (e.g., training data and models) or more efficient AI solutions (e.g., energy consumption).

A basis for such agreements is summarized in a PID Policy for the EOSC Federation prepared by OAEG1. For its governance (e.g., procedures for PID policy updates) as well as for assessment options (e.g., conformance “certification”), alternatives have been discussed and recommendations for consideration were made.

Further work: (1) monitor and prioritize PID-related outcomes of EOSC-projects that can support implementation of PIDs in the EOSC Federation; (2) investigate relevant PID services that can advance the Federation, and (3) focus on PID information about the digital objects’ persistence in LTDR workflows.

Table 3: Recommendations, desired activities and outcome for Persistent Identifiers (PIDs)

SP	Recommendation	Desired Activities and Outcomes
SP1	Finalise EOSC PID policy	Meetings, f2f workshop
	Identify PID-related KERs from projects that should be adopted by the Federation	Table/resource identifying project KERs related to PIDs (to be discussed in OAEG meetings)
	Align EOSC PID system with related initiatives in other parts of the world (CODATA, RDA, World Data System)	Liaise with international initiatives
	Clarify adoption of Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT) by EDEN and FIDELIS	Liaise with EDEN and FIDELIS/invite project representatives to join OAEG
	Machine actionability + Retrieval-Augmented Generation readiness	Explore the readiness for machine actionability and Retrieval-Augmented Generation, identifying key opportunities for integration and enhancement
	Map data types and communities, challenges, CARE & TRUST	Facilitate a broad exploration of diverse data types, relevant communities, and associated challenges, incorporating principles of CARE and TRUST
	Provide feedback and recommendations on data retention and (re)appraisal	To be given to EOSC-A BoD and projects EDEN & FIDELIS.
	Finalise TF LTDR charter	Online meetings, perhaps f2f

SP2	Promote an EOSC-wide PID Policy as fundamental for the EOSC Federation	Liaise with EOSC Partnership Tripartite Governance to devise a path to finalise the EOSC PID Policy
	PIDs mentioned at national/institutional level in MAR, but consider EU-level recommendation in the future EOSC documents (e.g. SRIA2.0).	Engage in community consultation and other EOSC-A initiatives
SP3/4	Produce a PID glossary aligned with LTDR vocabulary	Harmonize the vocabulary of LTDR and the glossary of the PID Policy with others, e.g. EOSC Glossary
	Re-appraisal workflow should point to PID policy and recommendations about how to manage PIDs for data that are deleted/transferred/updated	Develop guidance on integrating PID policy into re-appraisal workflows, ensuring clarity on PID management for data that is deleted, transferred, or updated
	Broadening OAEG1 with supply-side (providers). Include more end-users (communities).	To be explored and planned

2.3.2 Interoperability in EOSC (OAG2+TF1+TF3)

For EOSC to become a cornerstone in the European research landscape, the emerging web of FAIR data and services must be able to demonstrate that it provides added value through a compelling showcase of use cases that show how seamless integration of resources and research infrastructures contributes to efficient research. As the EOSC Federation takes shape, a shared understanding of interoperability will become increasingly important to enable resource discovery, access to resources, or the integration of data and services. Clarifying the governance of the Interoperability Framework itself would be equally important. Documenting the process that is used to determine the content of the IF framework would make it easier to determine what are the key features that would form the basis for EOSC compliance assessment. The discussions held in the group updated the stakeholder landscape and their needs (represented by the scientific use cases and stories), solutions, and building blocks. The recommendations produced will contribute to building a shared technically and semantically interoperable architecture for EOSC that enables automated resource integration and compatibility across tools, services and data processing workflows, while also supporting organisational and legal interoperability. The group plans to generate a new version of the EOSC Interoperability Framework, adapted to the future EOSC Federation⁷, as well as to explore and align with the Interoperability Frameworks of other EOSC-related activities.

In addition to reviewing the inventory of the Opportunity Area Expert Group 2 activities, the breakout sessions generated two ad hoc repositories of interoperability solutions as collective landscaping activities during the sessions. The topics of these repositories were:

- [Collection of existing solutions with basic metadata](#) (origins, links to background material, contact persons) mapped to EOSC Interoperability Framework challenges. The spreadsheet generated during the session includes over 140 solutions.
- [Projects and interested parties contributing to the web of FAIR data and the uptake of AI](#) (initial categorisation and metadata schema with six specific examples)

The following table serves as a snapshot of some of the recommendations, potential activities, and desirable outcomes that were discussed during the three sessions. This can serve as input

⁷ A draft roadmap can be found in the [reporting slides](#) for SP3/SP4.

to plan future coordination across the HE EOSC projects, EOSC Association and the wider EOSC stakeholder community.

Table 4: Recommendations, desired activities and outcome for Interoperability in EOSC

SP	Recommendation	Desired Activities and Outcomes
SP1	Produce a clear map of solutions towards EOSC projects and TFs & Alignment with the EOSC IF Registry	Update and curate the collaborative table of solutions mapped to the identified (semantic, technical) interoperability problems in the EOSC IF document ⁸
	More focus on user perspective	Continue the work on user stories started during the afternoon session (day 1)
	More synchronization & collaboration meetings	Update OAEg meeting schedule for 2025 (including milestones, actions, responsibilities); explore other formats (e.g. workshops)
	Continue the started work in the OAEg2 and TFs	Schedule & host regular meetings, invite TF representatives to attend
	Develop a sustained approach to sharing resources across OAs and TFs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Share the following resources: • Contributors to the web of FAIR data and the uptake of AI • Collaborative table of interoperability solutions • Collaborative table of interoperability Use Cases
SP2	Focus on metadata, metadata curation and validation, and coherent FAIR approaches to ensure quality of training and evaluation data	Build benchmarks to evaluate models
	Theoretical discussions vs pragmatic solutions to keep up with the US and other regions: collect examples of current use of AI in science (use cases, caveats and “don’t use” cases).	Start a document collecting examples (e.g. problem/use case, solution name, description, & link, plus “caveats”)
	Ongoing developments to track: FAIR for AI (Scientific Knowledge Graphs, semantic artefacts) and AI for FAIR (metadata quality assessment using LLMs, mappings) need to happen. What is “FAIR enough” for AI?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Start a document collecting research outputs on FAIR for AI/AI for FAIR. • Explore FAIR enough for AI by way of contributions from OAEg members • We need to collect use cases, caveats and “don’t use” cases about AI is being used in projects
SP3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interoperability solutions need to be curated and maintained - The “yellow pages” created in the WS session (142 entries) is already a considerable challenge to curate and assess • Lightweight governance to drive adoption and convergence 	(EOSC Fed H vs SIMPL) Create a common appendix that describes alignment, synergies and actors

⁸ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, EOSC Executive Board, Corcho, O., Eriksson, M., Kurowski, K. et al., *EOSC interoperability framework – Report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Groups FAIR and Architecture*, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/620649>.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The number of actors and complexity of the landscape requires flexibility and dynamism ○ Important to provide tools, standards, support, incentives ● Cross-link the EOSC Federation handbook and public SIMPL specification (a common appendix describing alignment, synergies and actors?) 	
	Use frameworks such as the Cross-domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF) to break down the interoperability challenge into manageable components and document the choices made.	Cross-reference the interoperability solutions table with the CDIF
SP4	The lack of fully formalised definitions and implementation plans of EOSC and data spaces provide an opportunity to build interoperability solutions and demonstrators.	Update collaborative table of interoperability solutions mapped to the identified (semantic, technical) interoperability problems with implementation plans
	Engagement between EOSC and Data Spaces is needed before bridging approaches and definition/selection of open standards and APIs can proceed efficiently.	Invite Common European Data Spaces representatives to join OAEG2 or other OAEGs
	EOSC is not only for researchers, and Data Spaces are not only for industry.	Find common ground and shared standards.
	Brokers and middleware (SIMPL) to act as middlemen to persuade providers to adopt standards. SIMPL could serve as a protocol to connect data spaces/ as the common ground.	OAEGs and TFs to collect the needs of the two communities (academia/industry)
	Incubate and scale up the innovative research solutions.	Link Data Spaces with EOSC

2.3.3 FAIR assessment and data objects (OAEG3+TF2+TF4)

The sessions explored the evolving landscape of FAIR data, addressing current limitations and highlighting opportunities created by emerging standards and improved data quality to enhance reuse and preservation. The focus was put on FAIR assessment, metrics, data quality, and the uptake of AI-ready FAIR data in the EOSC Federation, which requires to align efforts across projects to improve FAIRness and streamline FAIR practices for Digital Objects. To advance the application of the FAIR principles, it is necessary to further develop and align assessment tools and methods and their role in ensuring the quality, curation and preservation of Digital Objects. Participants received insights by experts on practical implementation for FAIR assessment. The aim is to support consistent FAIR assessment across repositories, projects and communities by fostering a unified and transparent framework, and to provide guidance for its implementation within and outside of the EOSC community.

Table 5: Recommendations, desired activities and outcome for FAIR Assessment and Data Objects

SP	Recommendation	Desired Activities and Outcome
SP1	Define who is responsible for metadata (repositories, authors, Standardisation Org)	Align with the work of the EDEN and FIDELIS projects on a Framework for core preservation and a matrix of repository attributes. Align these activities and functions with which actors, agents have specific rights and responsibilities.
	AI needs quality, but data quality is not the same as FAIRness. FAIR is key for transparency (provenance, reusability, etc.) → Transparency for Trust	Improve transparency of practice by implementing and promoting the framework and matrix (above) to provide clear references to differentiate technical quality (compliance with criteria) from 'scientific' quality (fitness for purpose).
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Align, adapt, improve criteria for FAIRness; Develop customized advice on FAIRness [TF FMDO, TF LTDR] Align repositories & objects perspectives [TF LTDR] 	Align with the work of the TFs FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects/Long-term Data Retention to update criteria for FAIRness
SP2	Clarify the role of FAIR in AI (data quality vs reproducibility vs reusability)	Align with (new) projects working on data quality but not specific to AI (e.g. EOSC Eden)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Legal and Accessibility issues of datasets for AI models: How to harmonize access conditions for letting agents what to use FAIR should help using the right data for the right purpose Understand risks/misuse of data for an AI model 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop an ODRL profile for dealing with AI data specific conditions Align with EOSC Entrust Align with FAIRCORE4EOSC and RO-Crate who support 5safes concepts for sensitive data
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define what AI-ready means to understand whether FAIR can help make data AI-ready (AI-ready often requires cleaning and integration, which FAIR does not address) ML models should be FAIR (and with transparent provenance) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extend FAIRness for AI to address minimum metadata: Completeness of AI datasets (missing values, imputation strategies, biases) Variable description Representation format Relevant projects: Croissant data standard adoption FAIR4ML and crosswalks effort AI4EOSC (?)
	Extend FAIRness for AI to address minimum metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure completeness of AI datasets (missing values, imputation strategies, biases) Variable description Representation format Make ML models FAIR (with transparent provenance)
Incorporate AI as a search engine/curator of metadata (keywords / categories)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define the role of AI in steering data spaces mappings (e.g. keyword/taxonomy based) Assess AI as a recommender for selecting the right taxonomies (if they exist) AI as a means to improve existing metadata (e.g., descriptions) 	

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AI as a flagging system that needs human intervention FAIRCORE4EOSC has MSCR, which could be used as a foundation for AI to populate mappings
SP3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop a common model for metrics, tests and associated benchmarks across FAIR tools Defining authority for selecting metrics and defining community benchmarks Interoperability: Common approach to FAIR across Spaces where possible, transparency of local/specific FAIR criteria where necessary 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Align with Skills4EOSC, Medical Informatics Initiative including FAIR metrics design, EHDS (legal framework) Build on the work of OSTrails assessment framework.
SP3/4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Share FAIR Digital Object assessment outcomes: fulfilling the FAIR contract Quality control & certification of tests vs reliance on transparency 	Phases of FAIR Spaces: Internal engagement decisions on validation and authority for relevant metrics and benchmarks > adoption and implementation in production > more public outcomes of FAIR Assessment
SP4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sovereignty and Security as extensions of rights & access, cf. EHDS Roadmap Spaces approach to FAIRness inclusive of special category data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased common reference points and consistency of outcomes across FAIR assess tools [OSTrails] Modelling and specification of FAIR overall metrics and community specific benchmarks [TF 2 & 4 + OA3] Exposure of relevant metadata at object and repository level to enable assessment with associated guidance and assistance for corrective actions
	Data Spaces as aggregators of metadata, selectors of digital objects for relevance (incl. FAIRness), generators of derived digital objects within the data space (how FAIR?)	Align the evolution of data spaces with transparent FAIR assessment for a (rapidly approaching) world of domain-specific and object-specific testing

2.3.4 User and resource environments - Trusted VREs and the EOSC Federation (OAEG4+TF1+TF3)

The EOSC Federation Model was presented in this group as a guide on the technical requirements for service providers (including those of Virtual Research Environments) to join the EOSC Federation. This included discussing the technical procedures to “enrol” the Federation as a Node, or to onboard services to an EOSC Node. Other topics were sustainable community spaces and “subdomains”, advanced integration of data via Zenodo or Copernicus, AI and its relation to the FAIR principles, and contributions of the Galaxy Training Network to sustainable and interoperable research. Trusted VREs were demonstrated to provide federated and interoperable systems to link with the Common European Data Spaces, since they allow for securely identifying, sharing, processing, and reusing of (FAIR) data. The discussions also covered the EOSC Federation Handbook and the first experiences from the EOSC Beyond pilots.

The session reviewed the EOSC Federation Model, showing the federating capabilities that will follow the testing of new multi-node use cases by EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox

services. Initial integration efforts for infrastructure and application services were also evaluated between participating projects and the EOSC EU Node, addressing technical and non-technical limitations. Key recommendations include further integration of open-source tools to distribute AI models between platforms as well as collaboration to establish robust Trusted VREs between relevant projects.

Table 6: Recommendations, desired activities and outcome for User and Resource environments – Trusted VREs and the EOSC Federation

SP	Recommendation	Desired Activities and Outcomes
SP1	Work with a shared model for the EOSC Technical Architecture Develop a common vocabulary	Follow what EOSC Federation Handbook says on this
	EOSC EU Node: More automation is needed / Not enough credits for meaningful research	Propose an improved credits model for the EOSC EU Node
	Clearly communicate current objectives and target users	Define a communication strategy
SP2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> User credentials to access data between cloud storage systems used in the EOSC EU Node and AI4EOSC platforms (webdav) Scaling: be ready for success. At some point we need to get back to “strace” again. Software quality varies between 3500 tools - debugging? 	Explore further integration between platforms incl. the EOSC EU Node to increase FAIRness
	What is the necessity of LLM in EOSC? Can/should EOSC offer data-private LLM services?	Start a working paper on LLMs in EOSC
SP3	Define a harmonised operational and legal framework to facilitate the secure sharing and governance of, and access to, data and services (LLM services and models, research sovereignty, data security, technological dependency; TRE relationships and policy harmonization; data sensitivity levels as a dynamic concept, to be defined in a machine-actionable way; data anonymization tools for the data owner/rights holder) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of harmonized metadata (e.g. in AI models) → crosswalks Responsibility and liability for sensitive data disclosure, even if anonymized 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define clear channels to provide feedback & recommendations on EOSC Nodes services Clarify with the EOSC EU Node and EOSC Beyond the (non-)technical issues when integrating or leveraging EOSC Nodes assets & acceptable use Explore additional interoperability opportunities between INFRAEOSC projects (esp. on AI assets, but not only)
	Interoperability as a key asset for sustainability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Curated and quality metadata is key for interoperability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaboration between TRE projects LLM services available as a preview for EOSC
SP4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> VREs are often domain-specific, suitable for Thematic Nodes Connectors (e.g. SIMPL) overarching Data Spaces between EOSC, Health (TF) and Green Deal (SAGE) with a use case on air quality 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explore the usability of the EOSC EU Node to connect other CEDS with user stories that start from VREs in INFRAEOSC projects. Integrate tools with Galaxy platform using existing standards such as OGC API Processes (e.g. AquaINFRA and Blue-Cloud)

2.3.5 Skills & engagement (OAE5)

Making Open Science the new normal is one of the fundamental objectives of the SRIA. The activities of OAE5 are essential for this to happen, ensuring research communities and supporting data stewards are aware, engaged, skilled and rewarded for practising Open Science. In 2024, OAE5 identified four Workstreams: Strategy and Engagement; Rewards & Recognition; Training Catalogue/Training Infrastructure; and Training Material/Curriculum/Learning Paths. During the Winter School, OAE5 discussed the work done in 2024 in the light of the four Strategic Pillars and established its priorities for 2025. One priority will be to clarify the roles and definitions of competence centres in the EOSC ecosystem, particularly in relation to EOSC Nodes, taking previous work by Skills4EOSC into account. Efforts will also be made to scope the need for an EOSC Training Catalogue, by identifying end-user needs and improving the visibility of existing resources. Additionally, OAE5 will continue to engage with all actors in the EOSC ecosystem to increase adoption of Open Science, including strengthening collaboration with CoARA⁹ by focusing on the recognition and rewards infrastructure.

It was recognised that many OAE5 activities cut across all strategic pillars and this will be carefully considered when structuring future work plans by pillar. It was also agreed to change the name of the group to reflect the key outcomes desired by the group - to develop *skills*, facilitate *engagement*, and increase *adoption* of EOSC. (The current name is a combination of four different task force names - 'Skills, Training, Rewards, Recognition and Upscaling').

Table 7: Recommendations, desired activities and outcomes for Skills & Engagement

SP	Recommendation	Desired Activities and Outcomes
SP1	Close the communication gap about the EOSC Skills & Engagement & Adoption between OAE5 & EOSC-A Board	Reinstall liaison role to improve communication with the EOSC-A Board of Directors. Update: OAE5 coordinators / chairs have now been invited to the regular meetings between TF chairs and the EOSC-A Board. Liaison roles were not possible due to Board member capacity.
	Further clarify definitions & implementations of Competence Centres, including their relation to EOSC Nodes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Convene discussion around relationship between Competence Centres and Nodes, aligning with existing activities in the EOSC-A, OSCARS and Skills4EOSC • Bring parties together and create an overview of the various Competence Center definitions or approaches taking the emerging EOSC nodes into consideration. • Check the EuroHPC National Competence Centres since they are the equivalent to a CC for some countries • Continue liaison with the S4EOSC competence centre network
	Continue to work closely with the EOSC Association and EOSC Focus / Gravity projects to support ongoing engagement activities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintain contacts with EOSC Association and EOSC Focus throughout the transition to EOSC Gravity • Restart regular exchanges of activities around approaches to engagement and

⁹ <https://coara.eu/>

		strategy in countries and domains (previously run by the Upskilling Countries Task Force).
	Analyse and contribute to the recommendations in the EOSC Federation Handbook on Engagement, Skills and Training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define the scope and added value of each OAE5 workstream, considering past and existing engagement activities and the gaps to be addressed, and complement with other engagement activities. Identify topics for HE WP 2025 EOSC calls focusing on training and engagement to understand EC priorities
SP2	Analyze, align and adopt rewards and recognition mechanisms in EOSC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support new recognition and reward practices & infrastructure to incentivise adoption of EOSC Catalogue and analyse emerging recognize/reward projects/pilots/practices that aim to incentivise adoption of EOSC to identify gaps and opportunities. Review the (Open Science) Action Plan by the Commission to implement the ten commitments of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA)¹⁰
	Define the vision for the EOSC Training Catalogue(s): What is needed, for whom, and which route are they following to get there	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Build on EOSC-Future's Training Catalogue & define a vision for the EOSC Training Catalogue: what is needed, for whom, and which route are they following to get there Liaise with EOSC EU Node to explore possibilities to add Training Resources, for example registering Training Catalogues in the EOSC EU Node as first step towards federating Training Catalogues Discuss within the OAE5 Engagement and Strategy workstream how to engage with organisations and researchers needed to raise awareness about training opportunities in the EOSC EU Node Align with EOSC Gravity to understand the planned EOSC Academy
	Align existing methods to create Learning Paths and map them	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> OAE5EG to learn from cross-border training initiatives in the RIs (including Australia) Check with Skills4EOSC sustainability plans Find out how much of CPD¹¹ for data stewards exists in countries and institutes How can AI extract metadata from training resources while preserving the data quality?
SP3	Encourage policymakers to review & adjust national policies, funding, and regulations, and develop training programmes that enable resources to be used cross-border and -domain, preserving data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> OAE5EG can support activities of other TFs and OAE5s in this area but will not take a leading role should not lead in shaping activity on a national level in research security and sovereignty

¹⁰ Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment

¹¹ Continuing Professional Development, see <https://www.cpduk.co.uk/explained>.

	sovereignty and ensuring broader interoperability and accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● OAEG5 can contribute activities, e.g. by including skills & training in National Tripartite Events ● Connect to organisations like EARMA¹² to avoid duplication of efforts ● Continue to liaise with future projects or other initiatives that may produce training
	Offer training, CPD; install procedures to select and curate research outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Help disseminate information and resources to countries and institutes ● Establish state-of-the art, create overview, support discussions to harmonise efforts ● Identify demonstrators and use cases
SP4	Leverage existing national Competence Centres and strengthen their participation in coordination networks at EU level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Clarify the definition of national Competence Centres before planning actions ● OAEG5 to help align with discussions about competence centres within EOSC, including EOSC Nodes
	Promote participation in Data Spaces, EU missions, and European Partnerships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Strengthen examples of ongoing OA5-related activities (e.g. INRAE with standards in Agridataspaces) ● Liaise with Health Data Task Force
Overarching	Refine and prioritise ideas and suggestions from WS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Optimise text in the EOSC Federation Handbook to include recommendations on skills, training and engagement ● Expand network to accelerate engagement and adoption (e.g. EARMA, EUA, research communities...) ● Update OAEG5 web page with relevant reports ● Take forward Competence Centre discussions. Further connect with relevant RDA groups: 1) Education and Training on Handling of Research Data IG; 2) Professionalising Data Stewardship IG

2.3.6 Integrating open scholarly communication with EOSC (OAEG6+TF1+TF2)

OAEG6 deals with Open Scholarly Communication (OSC)¹³. OSC is the system through which research and other scholarly writing is created, evaluated, disseminated to the scholarly community, and preserved for future use. Open Access models and their corresponding information infrastructures (e.g. pre-print and deposition portals; Open Peer Review channels; Gold, Green and Diamond Open Access; Digital libraries such as PubMed Central; publishers) are key elements for OSC together with the development of an action plan fostering collaborative processes. The sessions brought together key stakeholders from various domains to address the integration and advancement of OSC within EOSC. By embracing an integrative approach to diverse forms of scientific records OSC can support the development and sustainability of collaborative scientific infrastructures. In recognition of the increasing global significance of the Diamond Open Access model, as supported by the EC or UNESCO, the

¹² The European Association of Research Managers and Administrators, see <https://earma.org/>.

¹³ For an overview of OSC in EOSC, see e.g. <https://eosc.eu/eosc-focus-project/winter-school-2025/integrating-open-scholarly-communication-within-eosc>

sessions seek to establish a robust framework for OSC. In brief, the session focused on integrating and advancing OSC within EOSC.

Table 8: Recommendations, desired activities and outcome for Integrating Open Scholarly Communication with EOSC

SP	Recommendation	Desired Activities and Outcome
SP1	Establish a continuum of FAIR - open - scholarly data in EOSC & make sure that the services exist around them	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardise services into so that they can contribute to the EOSC Federation • Communities to converge towards standards (e.g., JATS XML, BioC), guidelines, commons (e.g., OSTrails IRA & Commons) • Realise machine-actionable DOs (e.g. XML based) • Create a virtuous circle among adoption and sustain at different levels (by institution, countries etc.)
	Establish OSC services, resources and standards as used across EOSC nodes to address sustainability of meta frameworks such as the EOSC Federation we need to address practicalities such as user uptake of standards in publishing and OSC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spell out how EOSC nodes and their services cover OSC • Identify OSC-related standards, established processes and controlled vocabularies
SP2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use metadata to describe the link between publications, research data, supplementary data & data availability statements • European Diamond Capacity Hub (built in DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA) should become a thematic node of the EOSC Federation in near future as a “voice of publication within the federation” • OAE6 should play an important role in discussing publications as Digital Objects of interest in EOSC - similar function as OAE7 is doing for research software. • Data dissemination and publishing criteria should be part of data stewardship courses. • Some lightweight training in repository and library publishing would help to become more engaged in EOSC and the research data domain. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss with the EOSC EU Node how to connect Diamond Discovery Hub to the Resource Hub • Discuss semantic interoperability issues between publications and data at the TF1 Semantic Interoperability subgroup meeting • Liaise with OAE5 on training in repository and library publishing

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establish forum within OA6 to identify key standards of forums relevant for publishing industries 	
Overarching	<p>Clarify the role of machine actionability of digital objects in OSC (what are our observable data points?) → understanding and agreeing on agnostic descriptors of values enables machine actionability and AI readiness</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Share use cases, application profiles Identify shared characteristics of research output types (e.g. datasets, supplements, publications) Identify interoperable schemata esp around metadata → essential for OSC and data spheres as they are all research outputs
SP3	<p>Transfer approved practices from one domain to the other (e.g. what is granularity, what are relations)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “Tough love” – similar to interdisciplinary research, with the support of trained experts, get stakeholders to agree on concepts of security or sharing at the start, insist on practical levels of standardisation) Include these aspects in curricula for Data Stewards and OSC professionals (Liaise with OAE5) Broaden the idea of Data Management Plans to Object Management Plans Identify reasons to meet and keep on working together
SP3/4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agreement that gatekeepers, trust and tokens for quality are required for research security and sovereignty and its upscaling Interoperability and FAIRification enable gatekeeping “what is gated, by whom, how and why” which in OSC enables research security and clarity on sovereignty Implement best practices across disciplines 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Break down values such as quality, quality control (such as peer review), trust, security into descriptors and transparent ways of assessing them to enable uptake across disciplines and bridge the gap between data spheres and publishing spheres Trust can percolate along the stream of interoperability, FAIR spelled out can serve as an a priori setting of security While discipline specifics are important, several best practices can be ported across disciplines Data flows and data governance can be adapted for and adopted in other contexts

2.3.7 Research software (OAE7)

This new OAE7 had its first in-person session at the 2025 WS, with the primary goal of identifying a roadmap of actions to address the challenges and opportunities around research software in EOSC. Following up on the virtual kick-off in early January, the group mapped the priorities of the Strategic Pillar on the OAE7’s scope and created a template to capture software-related outputs and activities across EOSC. The group will work to ensure that research software

is explicitly tackled in the EOSC SRIA and MAR, especially around reproducibility and transparency aspects. This will be achieved by reviewing all EOSC-project activities, highlighting how research software is currently considered (and especially if it is overlooked), as well as updating the figure where the actors in the EOSC ecosystem are shown¹⁴ to reflect software-related aspects properly.

Table 9: Recommendations, desired activities and outcomes for Research Software

SP	Recommendation	Desired Activities and Outcomes
SP2/3/4	Ensure that software is not neglected in SRIA	Engage in community consultation and other EOSC-A initiatives
	Update the actor ecosystem figure to reflect software aspects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continue mapping exercise • Produce a Zotero library and a processable version of the data
	Go through all EOSC-project activities and highlight the extent to which research software is currently overlooked	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Produce overview of Software in EOSC projects

¹⁴ SRIA 1.3, p. 117, Figure 6.1: Actors in the EOSC ecosystem: roles and interactions.

3 Opening session: Latest developments in the EOSC ecosystem

The Winter School opened with a warm welcome by EOSC-A General Secretary Ute Gunsenheimer, setting the stage for three days of collaborative exchange and knowledge sharing. The opening session introduced the key themes shaping the evolving EOSC ecosystem, with a particular focus on their impact on EOSC-related Horizon Europe projects. Karel Luyben (EOSC-A President) provided an in-depth examination of the four Strategic Pillars underpinning the EOSC Partnership, highlighting their role in driving the federation's development. This was followed by updates on:

- EOSC-A Task Forces presented by Ignacio Blanquer (EOSC-A BoD)
- Opportunity Area Expert Groups (OAEs) presented by Ilire Hasani-Mavriqi (EOSC Focus)
- EOSC-A's approach to enhancing the sustainability and impact of EOSC-related project results, presented by Ilaria Nardello (EOSC-A)

A key message emphasised was the importance of aligning key exploitable results from projects with the EOSC Federation's priorities to ensure their added value. It was underlined that project beneficiaries must actively take ownership of their results and commit to identifying pathways for their exploitation. The timing to leverage project outcomes is particularly favourable, as the first HE EOSC-related projects are concluding just as the EOSC Federation is taking its first steps.

The opening plenary continued with updates on the EOSC Federation and the EOSC EU Node, offering insights into the latest developments in the federation's build-up phase. Bob Jones (EOSC-A BoD) presented the current understanding of the principles underpinning the EOSC Federation¹⁵, followed by an update on the EOSC EU Node¹⁶ by Peter Szegedi (DG-CONNECT). Javier López Albacete (DG-RTD) and Andy Götz (EOSC-A), the leading editor of the EOSC Federation Handbook, provided perspectives on the Federation's build-up phase¹⁷ from the Tripartite Group¹⁸. Their presentations outlined the enrolment process for candidate EOSC Nodes and highlighted the EOSC Federation Handbook as a key reference framework, guiding the Federation's operations, architecture, policies, and scientific services throughout its build-up phase.

The session concluded with a panel discussion on converging towards the EOSC Federation, chaired by Ute Gunsenheimer and featuring Bob Jones, Peter Szegedi, and Javier López Albacete. A key takeaway from the discussion was the importance of initiating sustainable exploitation planning early in the project lifecycle, with active engagement from all partners. The EOSC Macro-Roadmap¹⁹ was highlighted as a unique tool to showcase both expected and delivered project outcomes, helping to map exploitable results against the Federation's evolving needs.

A central message conveyed was the need for EOSC-related projects to explore whether their key exploitable results could be "adopted" by the emerging EOSC Nodes, paving the way for their

¹⁵ <https://eosc.eu/building-the-eosc-federation/>.

¹⁶ <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/>.

¹⁷ <https://bit.ly/Enrolment-of-candidate-EOSC-Nodes>.

¹⁸ The Tripartite Group was set up by the EOSC Partnership Tripartite Governance to prepare common positions and support the Governance establish the EOSC Federation (see e.g., https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/20240620_S4_Towards-an-operational-EOSC-Federation.pdf).

¹⁹ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-macro-roadmap/>.

long-term sustainability. The pivotal role of the EOSC EU Node was once again emphasised as a cornerstone in the federation's gradual build-up.

4 Closing plenary: How to enhance the EOSC Federation

The closing plenary started with a presentation by Ilaria Nardello (EOSC Association), who addressed the sustainability of project results within the context of the EOSC Federation. This was followed by Evdokimos Konstantinidis (RAISE), who shared practical examples of exploiting project results, drawing on insights and experiences from the RAISE project.

The 2025 EOSC Winter School was concluded with a panel discussion chaired by Karel Luyben, featuring representatives from the seven Programme Subcommittees, as follows:

- Tibor Kálmán - PIDs
- Simon Hodson - Interoperability in EOSC
- Daniel Garijo - FAIR Assessment and Data Objects
- Amanda Calatrava - User and Resource Environments: Trusted VREs and the EOSC Federation Model
- Celia van Gelder – Skills & Engagement
- Patrick Ruch - Integrating OSC within EOSC
- Fotis Psomopoulos - Research Software

The panel reiterated the outcomes of the individual breakout sessions, placing emphasis on how to strengthen the EOSC Federation by addressing the concrete action points developed by the Opportunity Areas Expert Groups and EOSC-A Task Forces. Panellists were asked to elaborate on the outcomes/recommendations that had been presented during the reporting sessions and dealt with Strategic Pillar 1 – Sustaining and Enhancing the EOSC Federation.

The panel reiterated that the EOSC Federation should adopt a common **PID Policy** and have the authority to mandate its implementation. The current diversity of PID systems, many of which are not resolvable and not persistent, must be addressed to create a coherent landscape. This could be achieved through getting PID providers and authorities involved in OAEG1, and employing the PID Policy to ensure the compliance of EOSC Nodes that become part of the EOSC Federation. To facilitate this, the PID Policy should be included in the EOSC Federation Handbook, and compliance with it should be one of the technical requirements to join the EOSC Federation.

In their session, the **Interoperability in EOSC** group had listed solutions for the semantic (79 solutions, with 18 solutions completed or in progress at the time of the Winter School) respectively technical (54 solutions, with 13 completed or in progress at the time of the Winter School) interoperability layers defined in the EOSC Interoperability Framework (EOSC-IF), elaborating on the nature of the problems addressed, the envisioned providers of these solutions, and the target groups. The aim of the sessions had been to provide recommendations for each interoperability layer and to break down the problem space, to be able to incorporate the recommendations into the EOSC-IF and to link interoperability to the solutions developed by EOSC-related projects.

The sessions focused on the challenges in technical and semantic interoperability caused by the diversity of formats of research data. The diversity of PID systems and policies hampers technical interoperability, while semantic interoperability is hampered by lack of common definitions of terms used by user communities, semantic artefacts across communities (e.g., ontologies that can be shared), and semantic-related skills. Semantic interoperability suffers from lack of reference repositories/registries for semantic artefacts, with data collections often poorly documented (missing metadata, different metadata schemas across communities). Many of these problems are due to insufficient expertise and skills in semantics, insufficient knowledge of established domain and domain neutral schemas. There is also a need for a shift

from a bibliographic to an engineering approach to data stewardship, to address issues of data and metadata quality and to tackle interdisciplinary use cases.

Regarding technical interoperability, EOSC is expected to facilitate communities' access to resources through a common authentication and authorisation process. The multiple general-purpose formats and community-based models used for research data place a barrier for data reuse across communities. Here, improved systems to query repositories would enable data discovery. Also, it would help to unify PID policies and their enforcement and ensure all PID systems employed remain resolvable.

For **FAIR Assessment and Data Objects**, the EOSC Federation needs to clarify who is responsible for adding and maintaining. Currently, the responsibilities are split between repositories, owners of research outputs, standardisation organisations, or some other entity. Emerging standards and improved data quality should contribute to simplifying the evolving landscape of FAIR data, and to enhance reuse and preservation. Recommendations were given to the effect that FAIR assessment, metrics, data quality, and the uptake of AI-ready FAIR research data in the EOSC Federation will advance the application of the FAIR principles and ensure the quality and preservation of digital objects, supported by consistent FAIR assessment across projects and communities by fostering a unified and transparent framework.

The **Trusted VREs** group proposed to improve the EOSC EU Node by increasing automation, and by enabling researchers to upgrade their user credits to be able to use more resources as required by complex research projects, with the EOSC Federation Model acting as a guide on the technical requirements to join the EOSC Federation for infrastructure, VRE and other service providers. Efforts to integrate infrastructure and services between participating projects and the EOSC EU Node were evaluated, addressing technical and non-technical limitations. Key recommendations include further integration of open-source tools to distribute AI models between platforms as well as collaboration to establish robust Trusted VREs.

An important topic that was discussed in the **Skills and Engagement breakout session** related to the importance of formulating a vision for the EOSC Training catalogue(s). It needs to be clarified what end-users need and expect in this respect. The current EU Node only a very limited number of training resources and a first step that is needed and that will be explored is to make existing training catalogues visible and findable, either by registering them in the EU node and/or by developing a model to federate these existing Training Catalogues of RIs and projects. A second important action going forward is to contribute to clarifying the roles and definitions of the various competence centres in the EOSC ecosystem and their relation to EOSC Nodes. Finally, continued engagement with all actors in the EOSC ecosystem is needed to increase adoption, including strengthening collaboration with CoARA to put in place the necessary infrastructure to manage recognition and rewards.

The **Open Scholarly Communication within EOSC** group discussed how EOSC Nodes cover Open Scholarly Communication. To ensure the system works, Open Access models and their corresponding infrastructures must be in place, and more collaboration between them should be fostered. OSC can support the development and sustainability of collaborative scientific infrastructures if the EOSC Federation is able to integrate the current diversity of scientific records. The EOSC Federation should moreover recognise the increasing global significance of the Diamond Open Access model, supported by the EC and UNESCO, to establish a robust framework for OSC. A holistic approach considering all Open Access channels is needed. Further, the volume of supplementary data files is growing exponentially and should be turned into FAIR digital objects in relationship with full-text articles.

Last, the new **Opportunity Area Expert Group on research software**, which had kicked off in January 2025, elaborated on its goal of identifying actions to address the challenges and

opportunities related to research software in EOSC. Research software needs to be explicitly mentioned in the EOSC SRIA, especially the topics of reproducibility and transparency. In order to achieve this, OAEG7 will look into the activities of EOSC-related projects to learn how research software is currently considered, and especially if it is overlooked. Even if software is now widely recognised as critical for the advancement of research, there is currently no standard approach to ensure research software curation, quality, preservation, and adoption of best practices that can be used by all kinds of developers. Absence of credit and recognition systems for software itself and developers makes it more difficult to ensure sustainable software practices. OAEG7 intends to step into this void, building on prior work of the EOSC Infrastructures for Quality Research Software Task Force and the EOSC Scholarly Infrastructures for Research Software report (Architecture WG). The group will work with global initiatives and efforts in this domain, such as the SciCodes consortium, the Research Data Alliance (RDA) FAIR4RS and Software Source Code activities and the Research Software Alliance (ReSA).

5 Lessons learned and conclusion

The second edition of the EOSC Winter School provided ample opportunity to assess the progress achieved since the first one, sparking new collaborations between ongoing HE EOSC-related projects, and contributing to increased understanding of EOSC on the part of participants. The most salient results achieved by the Opportunity Area Expert Groups and EOSC-A Task Forces pertain to the four Strategic Pillars of EOSC.

As EOSC transitions towards a more stakeholder-driven approach, the associated problem spaces are continuously evolving in tandem with the emerging EOSC Federation. This dynamic environment has required the OAEGs to regularly update the problem definitions first identified during the inaugural EOSC Winter School.

The collaboration mechanisms established by the EOSC Focus project – particularly the Opportunity Area Expert Groups – along with the EOSC-A Task Forces have now gained broad acceptance within the community as essential instruments to deliver “one EOSC”. However, the increasing need for high-level integration across topics and the strong commitment of all actors calls for an adjusted pace of collaboration to effectively align with the fast-moving developments in the EOSC ecosystem.

Overall, feedback from participants on the 2025 EOSC Winter School, collected through various channels (including spoken feedback and Mentimeter feedback), was very positive. Several constructive points were raised:

- Breakout Sessions: very few EOSC-A Task Forces (e.g., Long-Term Data Retention TF, FAIR Assessment and Digital Objects TF) faced challenges with the session format, especially when paired with multiple OAEGs. A possible solution could be to restructure or group breakout rooms for more flexibility. Additionally, some participants felt that more time for reflection before plenary presentations would have been beneficial.
- Participation: Some suggested inviting more researchers/end users, and longer breaks could provide more networking opportunities. A larger venue may also be necessary to accommodate increased participation.
- Programme development: Many participants expressed a preference for more time to develop the programme, allowing the community to co-create the content. They also suggested earlier registration to finalize attendance, which would enable better planning and the involvement of a broader range of speakers. An important point raised was the need for greater clarity around central concepts such as the EOSC Federation and EOSC Nodes. Some participants also requested more on-site information about ongoing and past HE EOSC-related projects.

The 2025 EOSC Winter School reaffirmed its role as a key community event that fosters collaboration, knowledge exchange, and networking among participants. We would like to conclude this report with the closing remarks of EOSC-A President Karel Luyben:

“As we move forward, it is crucial that we build on the spirit of collaboration demonstrated at the Winter School, with our efforts converging toward a common goal. 2025 will be a defining year for the EOSC Federation with the first nodes set to enrol in the coming months. We are very happy to have the support of the community”.

6 Annex

6.1 Organisation of the 2025 EOSC Winter School: From Thessaloniki to Seville

2024 has been a defining year for the development of the EOSC Federation. Following the first EOSC Winter School in Thessaloniki in (29 January - 1 February 2024), key milestones include the EOSC Tripartite events in Brussels (April) and Budapest (November), the EOSC-A General Assembly in Leuven in May, the EC Meeting with INFRAEOSC Projects in Brussels in June, and the 2024 EOSC Symposium in Berlin in October, all the way to the second Winter School in January 2025 in Seville.

October also marked the launch of the EOSC EU Node, and the start of the EOSC Federation Handbook writing phase. The programme of the second edition of the EOSC Winter School centred on the Strategic Pillars defined in the Multi-annual Roadmap 2026-27 to organise the discussions. The Opportunity Area Expert Groups (OAEs) and the EOSC-A Task Forces—the “brain pool” of the EOSC Association—were invited to “translate” the challenges presented by the Strategic Pillars into thematic breakout sessions according to their respective fields of expertise.

Figure 1: Programme structure of the 2025 EOSC Winter School

6.2 Programme committee and programme subcommittees

The programme committee was formed by Karel Luyben (EOSC-A President), Ute Gunsenheimer (EOSC-A Secretary General and chair of the committee), Bob Jones (EOSC-A BoD), Ilire Hasani-Mavriqi, Stefan Reichmann, and Miguel Rey Mazón (EOSC Focus). Programme subcommittees were formed by pairing OA Expert Groups with EOSC-A Task Forces according to the specific objectives associated with the Strategic Pillars (with TFs represented across more than one OAE, see section 6.4). These consisted of:

- co-coordinators of the respective OAE
- co-chairs of the EOSC-A TFs (associated with the OAE)

- (at least) one representative of the EOSC-A Board of Directors (“EOSC-A Board Liaison”, one person per sub-committee)
- one facilitator (EOSC Focus, EOSC-A)

A dedicated page under the EOSC-A website²⁰ was published to inform participants of all relevant details, and to allow the larger EOSC-A community a glimpse on the preparations for the WS. The website contained a separate tab for each OA displaying specific instructions, a reading list of relevant documents, and the specific objectives to be reached by the end of the sessions, as prepared by the respective sub-committees.

The work programme was co-created by the programme subcommittees. In the programme, the Strategic Pillars correspond to four thematic blocks, which in turn correspond to three parallel breakout sessions: SP1 (Tuesday afternoon), SP2 (Wednesday morning), and SP3 and SP4 (Wednesday afternoon). Each thematic block was followed by a reporting plenary, where breakout session rapporteurs reported on the OAEs/TFs specific input to the SP at hand (See Figure 1 *Schematic layout of EOSC Winter School 2025*).

The final reporting session, organized as a panel discussion, was held on Thursday morning, and was reserved to recap the discussions in each OAE and to discuss the sustainability of Key Exploitable Results in the plenary. In this way, the Strategic Pillars formed the thematic bracket for the Winter School program, while enabling individual OAEs to organise breakout sessions and to provide thematically coherent insights on the four SPs from their perspectives.

The full composition of the subcommittees can be found below.

6.2.1 PIDs (OAE1+TF4)

Sub-committee members

- OAE1: Tibor Kálmán, Gorka Epelde Unanue, Marek Cebecauer, Themis Zamani, Wim Hugo, Nick Juty, Evdokimos Konstantinidis, Adam Vials Moore
- TF4: Jenny O’Neill, Ulf Jakobsson
- EOSC-A Board Liaison: Sara Garavelli

Support team

- EOSC-A: Brina Klemenčič
- EOSC Focus: Ilaria Nardello, Aneta Pazik, Monika Goral-Kurbiel, Klaudina Spiewak-Woityla, Patricia Padilla

6.2.2 Interoperability in EOSC (OAE2+TF1+TF3)

Sub-committee members

- OAE2: Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström, Esteban Gonzales Guardia, Mark Dietrich, Simon Hodson, Agnes Jasinska, Matti Heikkurinen, Alexandra Kokkinaki
- TF1: Diego Scardaci, Jiri Marek, Christos Kanellopoulos
- TF3: Lene Krøl Andersen, Petr Holub
- EOSC-A Board Liaison: Bob Jones, Ignacio Blanquer

²⁰ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-focus-project/winter-school-2025/>.

Support team

- EOSC Focus: Stefan Reichmann, Ilaria Nardello, Aneta Pazik, Monika Goral-Kurbiel, Klaudina Spiewak-Woityla, Patricia Padilla

6.2.3 FAIR assessment and data objects (OAEG3+TF2+TF4)

Sub-committee members

- OAEG3: Chris Schubert, Daniel Garijo Verdejo, Munazah Andrabi, Yusnelkis Guisado, Anca Hienola, Francesca Spataro, Cinzia Cappiello
- TF2: Mark Wilkinson, Elli Papadopoulou, Richard Dennis
- TF4: Jacques Flores, Hervé L'Hours
- EOSC-A Board Liaison: Klaus Tochtermann, Sara Garavelli

Support team

- EOSC-A: Paola Ronzino
- EOSC Focus: Ilaria Nardello, Aneta Pazik, Monika Goral-Kurbiel, Klaudina Spiewak-Woityla, Patricia Padilla

6.2.4 User and resource environments (OAEG4+TF1+TF3)

Sub-committee members

- OAEG4: Diego Scardaci, Björn Grüning, Amanda Calatrava, Alvaró Lopez Garcia, Marie Jossé, Sebastian Luna-Valero, Jérôme Detoc
- EOSC-A Board Liaison: Bob Jones, Ignacio Blanquer

Support team

- EOSC Focus: Kaori Otsu, Ilaria Nardello, Aneta Pazik, Monika Goral-Kurbiel, Klaudina Spiewak-Woityla, Patricia Padilla

6.2.5 Skills & engagement (OAEG5)

Sub-committee members

- OAEG5: Celia van Gelder, Helen Clare, Victoria Dominguez, Fotis Psomopoulos, Isabel Caetano
- EOSC-A Board Liaison: Marialuisa Lavitrano

Support team

- EOSC-A: Julia Prieß-Buchheit
- EOSC Focus: Ilaria Nardello, Aneta Pazik, Monika Goral-Kurbiel, Klaudina Spiewak-Woityla, Patricia Padilla

6.2.6 Integrating open scholarly communication within EOSC (OAEG6+TF1+TF2)

Sub-committee members

- OAEG6: Sona Arasteh, Margo Bargheer, Leonidas Psipiringas, Sy Holsinger, Patrick Ruch, Ekaterina Kutafina

- TF1: Diego Scardaci, Jiri Marek, Christos Kanellopoulos
- TF2: Elli Papadopoulou, Mark Wilkinson
- EOSC-A Board Liaison: Bob Jones, Klaus Tochtermann

Support team

- EOSC Focus: Suvini Lai, Dario Vins, Ilaria Nardello, Aneta Pazik, Monika Goral-Kurbiel, Klaudina Spiewak-Woityla, Patricia Padilla

6.2.7 Research software (OAE7)

Sub-committee members

- OAE7: Fotis Psomopoulos, Morane Gruenpeter

6.3 2025 EOSC Winter School – Programme

Monday, 20 January 2025

Time	Event	Event description	Room
16.00–18.30	Welcome registration &	The event begins with an evening reception and soft launch, featuring arrival and registration, networking opportunities, and informal drinks.	Hall Sherry
18.30–20.00	Welcome reception		Hall Sherry/ Terrazza Rocio

Tuesday, 21 January 2025

Time	Event	Speakers	Room
08.00–09.00	Registration		Hall Sherry
09.00–09.15	Welcome on behalf of the EOSC Association (Kick-off, Welcome, Outline, Goals)	Ute Gunsenheimer	NERJA
09.15–09.45	Update EOSC-A & Intro: Strategic Pillars (Priority Areas of the EOSC Multi-Annual Roadmap (MAR) 2026–2027)	Karel Luyben	
09.45–10.00	EOSC Association Task Forces: current results, highlights and the way forward	Ignacio Blanquer	
10.00–10.15	Opportunity Area Expert Groups	Ilire Hasani-Mavriqi	
10.15–10.30	EOSC Impact & Sustainability	Ilaria Nardello	
10.30–10.45	Coffee break & networking		Hall Sherry/ Terrazza Rocio
10.45–11.00	EOSC Federation Principles	Bob Jones	NERJA
11.00–11.20	Updates to the EOSC EU Node	Peter Szegedi	
11.20–11.35	Updates from the EOSC Federation build-up phase	Javier Lopez Albacete	
11.35–11.45	EOSC Federation Handbook	Andy Götz	
11.45–12.45	Panel Discussion – Convergence towards the EOSC Federation	Bob Jones, Javier López Albacete, Peter Szegedi	

12.45–14.00	Lunch		Hall Sherry/ Terrazza Rocio
14.00–15.30	SP1: Sustaining and enhancing the EOSC Federation	Designated Session Speakers	Breakout Rooms
15.30–16.00	Coffee break & networking		Hall Sherry/ Terrazza Rocio
16.00–17.00	SP1: Sustaining and enhancing the EOSC Federation	Designated Session Speakers	Breakout Rooms
17.00–18.00	SP1 plenary reporting	Designated Session Rapporteurs, all	NERJA
18.30	Social event: Guided walking tour of Seville		Hall Sherry
20.00	Gala Dinner (Abades Triana Restaurant)		

Wednesday, 22 January 2025

Time	Event	Speakers	Room
09.30–11.00	SP2: Contributing to the web of FAIR data and the uptake of AI	Designated Session Speakers	Breakout Rooms
11.00–11.15	Coffee break & networking		Hall Sherry/ Terraza Rocio
11.15–12.00	SP2: Contributing to the web of FAIR data and the uptake of AI	Designated Session Speakers	Breakout Rooms
12.00–13.00	SP2 plenary reporting	Designated Session Rapporteurs, all	NERJA
13.00–14.00	Lunch		Hall Sherry/ Terraza Rocio
14.00–15.30	SP3: Ensuring research security and sovereignty/SP4: Linking with other Common European Data Spaces and beyond	Designated Session Speakers	Breakout Rooms
15.30–16.00	Coffee break & networking		Hall Sherry/ Terraza Rocio

16.00–17.00	SP3: Ensuring research security and sovereignty/SP4: Linking with other Common European Data Spaces and beyond	Designated Session Speakers	Breakout Rooms
17.00–18.30	SP3 & SP4 plenary reporting, Introducing OA Expert Group 7 – Research Software	Designated Session Rapporteurs, OAEG7 co-chairs, all	NERJA

Thursday, 23 January 2025

Time	Title	Speakers	Room
09.30–09.35	Welcome & introduction	Karel Luyben	
09.35–10.20	Sustainability in EOSC	Ilaria Nardello	NERJA
10.20–11.20	Reporting on Strategic Pillars and Panel Discussion	Session Rapporteurs, chair: Karel Luyben	
11.20–11.30	Key outcomes, closing remarks & way forward	Karel Luyben	
11.30–13.00	Closing lunch		Hall Sherry/ Terrazza Rocio

6.4 Strategic Pillars: Pairing of priorities²¹, Opportunity Area Expert Groups, and EOSC-A Task Forces

6.4.1 Strategic Pillar 1 – Sustaining and enhancing the EOSC Federation

OAEG	EOSC-A Task Force	SP1: Sustaining and enhancing the EOSC Federation
1. PIDs	4. Long-Term Data Retention	A ²¹ , E

²¹ Capital letters denote the specific priorities pertaining to each of the four Strategic Pillars listed in the EOSC Multi-Annual Roadmap (MAR) for the years 2026 and 2027. The MAR 2026-2027 forms Section 8.1-8.4 of the [Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda](#) (SRIA 1.3). Priorities are assigned at three different implementation levels within each Strategic Pillar: European, national, and institutional.

2. Metadata, ontologies & interoperability	1. Technical & Semantic Interoperability 3. Health Data	A, B, E, G
3. FAIR Metric & Assessment	2. FAIR Metric and Digital Objects 4. Long-Term Data Retention	B, J
4. User & resource environments	1. Technical & Semantic Interoperability 3. Health Data	A, B, E
5. Skills & engagement		A, D, F, H, I
6. Open Scholarly Communication	1. Technical & Semantic Interoperability 2. FAIR Metric and Digital Objects	A, G
7. Research Software		B, E, G, J

6.4.2 Strategic Pillar 2 – Web of FAIR Data and the Uptake of AI

OAEG	EOSC-A Task Force	SP2: Contributing to the web of FAIR data and the uptake of AI
1. PIDs	4. Long-Term Data Retention	A, B, F, I, L
2. Metadata, ontologies & interoperability	1. Technical & Semantic Interoperability 3. Health Data	B, C, E, F, I
3. FAIR Metric & Assessment	2. FAIR Metric and Digital Objects 4. Long-Term Data Retention	A, C, F, I
4. User & resource environments	1. Technical & Semantic Interoperability 3. Health Data	B, C, D

5. Skills & engagement		G, H, J, K, M
6. Open Scholarly Communication	1. Technical & Semantic Interoperability 2. FAIR Metric and Digital Objects	B, D, F
7. Research Software		A, C, F, G, J

6.4.3 Strategic Pillar 3 – Research Security and Sovereignty

OAEG	EOSC-A Task Force	SP3: Ensuring research security and sovereignty
1. PIDs	4. Long-Term Data Retention	F
2. Metadata, ontologies & interoperability	1. Technical & Semantic Interoperability 3. Health Data	C
3. FAIR Metric & Assessment	2. FAIR Metric and Digital Objects 4. Long-Term Data Retention	
4. User & resource environments	1. Technical & Semantic Interoperability 3. Health Data	C, I, J
5. Skills & engagement		D, E, G, H, I, J
6. Open Scholarly Communication	1. Technical & Semantic Interoperability 2. FAIR Metric and Digital Objects	C
7. Research Software		G, F, H

6.4.4 Strategic Pillar 4 – Common European Data Spaces and beyond

OAEG	EOSC-A Task Force	SP4: Linking with other CEDS beyond
1. PIDs	4. Long-Term Data Retention	B
2. Metadata, ontologies & interoperability	1. Technical & Semantic Interoperability 3. Health Data	A, B, G
3. FAIR Metric & Assessment	2. FAIR Metric and Digital Objects 4. Long-Term Data Retention	
4. User & resource environments	1. Technical & Semantic Interoperability 3. Health Data	A, B, G
5. Skills & engagement		E, H
6. Open Scholarly Communication	1. Technical & Semantic Interoperability 2. FAIR Metric and Digital Objects	G
7. Research Software		B, E

6.5 List of participating projects

Project	Project/Technical Coordinator	Organisation	Website
AI4EOSC	Álvaro López García (coord.), Amanda Calatrava	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC), Universitat Politècnica de Valencia (UPV)	https://ai4eosc.eu/
Beyond Covid	Elaine Westwick	ELIXIR	https://by-covid.org/
BlueCloud2026	Sara Pittonet (coord.), Dick	CNR	https://www.blue-cloud.org/

	Schaap (techn. coord.)		
CLIMATEADAPT4EOSC	Thanasis Sfetsos	National Centre for Scientific Research "DEMOKRITOS"	https://climate-adapt4eosc.eu/
CRAFT-OA	Margo Bargheer (coord.), Sy Holsinger (techn. coord.)	Georg-August-Universität Göttingen	https://www.craft-oa.eu/
EOSC4CANCER	Salvador Capella (coord.)	Barcelona Supercomputing Center	https://eosc4cancer.eu/
EOSC Beyond	Hien Bui (coord.), Diego Scardaci (techn. coord.)	EGI	https://www.eosc-beyond.eu/
EOSC Eden	Damien LeCarpentier, Sara Garavelli	CSC	https://eosc.eu/eu-project/eosc-eden/
EOSC Entrust	Peter MacCallum (coord./techn. coord.)	ELIXIR Hub	https://eosc-entrust.eu/
EOSC Fidelis	Damien LeCarpentier, Sara Garavelli	CSC	https://eosc.eu/eu-project/fidelis/
EOSC Focus	Ute Gunsenheimer	EOSC Association	https://eosc.eu/eosc-focus-project/
EuroScienceGateway	Björn Grüning (coord.)	University of Freiburg	https://galaxyproject.org/projects/esg/
EVERSE	Fotis Psomopoulos (coord./techn. coord.), Salvador Capella-Gutierrez, Thanasis Vergoulis, Natalia Manola	CERTH	https://everse.software/

FAIRCORE4EOSC	Tommi Suominen (coord.), Mark van den sanden (techn. coord.)	CSC	https://faircore4eosc.eu/
FAIR-EASE	Alessandro Rizzo	CNRS	https://fairease.eu/
FAIR-Impact	Ingrid Dillo (coord.)	DANS	https://www.fair-impact.eu/
GraspOS	Thanasis Vergoulis (coord.), Clifford Tatum (techn. coord.)	Athena RC	https://graspos.eu/
OSCARS	Giovanni Lamanna (coord.)	CNRS-LAPP	https://oscars-project.eu/
OSTrails	Natalia Manola (coord.), Tomasz Miksa (techn. coord.)	OpenAIRE	https://ostrails.eu/
RAISE	Evdokimos Konstantinidis	Aristotle University Thessaloniki	https://raise-science.eu/
RDA Tiger			https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-tiger/
Skills4EOSC	Sara DiGiorgio (coord.)	GARR	https://www.skills4eosc.eu/
STR-ESFRI	Fotis Karayannis (coord.), Panagiota Koltsida (techn coord.)	Athena RC	https://www.esfri.eu/objectives-mission
TITAN	Antonio Skarmeta (coord./techn. coord.)	Universidad deMurcia	https://titan-eosc.eu/
WorldFAIR	Simon Hodson	CODATA	https://worldfair-project.eu/

6.6 Participants (per breakout session²²)

6.6.1 PIDs (OAEG1 + TF4)

First Name	Last Name	Organisation	Project(s)
Evdokimos	Konstantinidis	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	RAISE
Josefine	Nordling	CSC - IT Center for Science	FAIR-IMPACT
Wim	Hugo	DANS	FAIRCORE4EOSC
Rene	van Horik	DANS	FAIR-IMPACT
Mike	Bennett	DataCite	FAIRCORE4EOSC
Mejias	Gabriela	DataCite	FAIR-IMPACT
Brina	Klemenčič	EOSC Association	None
Gorka	Epelde	FUNDACION VICOMTECH	RAISE
Witold	Arndt	German Aerospace Center (DLR)	None
Miguel	Rey Mazón	TU Graz	EOSC-Focus
Themis	Zamani	GRNET	FAIRCORE4EOSC
Tibor	Kalman	GWDG	None
Jenny	O'Neill	HEAnet	None
Marek	Cebecauer	Heyrovsky Institute Prague	None
Ulriika	Vihervalli	National Library of Finland	FAIRCORE4EOSC
Sara	Ramezani	SURF	FAIR-IMPACT
Nick	Juty	The University of Manchester	FAIR-IMPACT
Ulf	Jakobsson	University of Gothenburg/Swedish National Data Service	None
Thierry	Carval	Ifremer/Euro-Argo ERIC	Blue Cloud 2026

²² The tables are based on the Winter School application forms. As participants were invited to move in between sessions, there may have been other people participating in the discussions at times.

Sara	Garavelli	EOSC Association, CSC - IT Center for Science	None
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6.6.2 Interoperability in EOSC (OAEG2 + TF1 + TF3)

First Name	Last Name	Organisation	Project(s)
Roksana	Wilk	ACC Cyfronet AGH	EOSC-Beyond
Mariarita	de Luca	AREA SCIENCE PARK	None
Petr	Holub	BBMRI-ERIC	EOSC4Cancer
Friederike	Schröder-Pander	Belnet	EOSC-Focus
Olivier	Rouchon	CNRS	FAIR-IMPACT
Matti	Heikkurinen	CODATA	FAIR-IMPACT
Simon	Hodson	CODATA	CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC
Liisa	Marjamaa-Mankinen	CSC - IT Center for Science	FAIR-IMPACT
Tommi	Suominen	CSC - IT Center for Science	FAIRCORE4EOSC
Ingrid	Dillo	DANS	FAIR-IMPACT
Vyacheslav	Tykhonov	DANS-KNAW	FAIR-IMPACT
Bo	Bai	DeiC	FAIR-IMPACT
Agnes	Jasinska	Digital Curation Centre, The University of Edinburgh	FAIR-IMPACT
Mark	Dietrich	EGI Foundation	EOSC-Beyond
Rudolf	Dimper	EOSC Association	EOSC-Focus
Andrew	Gotz	EOSC Association	OSCARS
Bob	Jones	EOSC Association	None
Karel	Luyben	EOSC Association	None
Ilaria	Nardello	EOSC Association	EOSC-Focus

Romain	David	ERINHA AISBL	OSCARS
Kamran	Naim	EOSC Association, CERN	None
Christos	Kanellopoulos	GEANT	None
Kostas	Koumantaros	GRNET	EOSC-Beyond
Philipp	Wieder	GWDG	FAIRCORE4EOSC
Laszlo	Kovacs	HUN-REN SZTAKI, Institute for Computer Science and Control	FAIR-IMPACT
Venkatesh	Kannan	ICHEC	None
Jiří	Marek	Masaryk University, Institute of Computer Science EOSC CZ	CRAFT-OA
Clement	Jonquet	MISTEA, INRAE	FAIR-IMPACT
Alexandra	Kokkinaki	National Oceanography Centre, British Oceanographic Data Centre	FAIR-EASE
Patrycja	Antosz	NORCE	None
Licia	Florio	EOSC Association, NORDUnet	None
Morten Wergeland	Hansen	Norwegian Meteorological Institute	None
Baptiste	Cecconi	Observatoire de Paris	OSTrails
Alex	Delipalta	RDA Association (RDA Europe)	RDA Tiger
Kurt	Baumann	Switch	FAIRCORE4EOSC
Majid	Ounsy	Synchrotron SOLEIL	OSTrails
Ilire	Hasani-Mavriqi	TU Graz	EOSC-Focus
Stefan	Reichmann	TU Graz	EOSC-Focus
Tomasz	Miksa	TU Wien & SBA Research	OSTrails
Esteban	González Guardia	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	FAIR-IMPACT
Thomas	Jouneau	Université de Lorraine / Recherche Data Gouv platform	EOSC-FIDELIS

Eli	Chadwick	University of Manchester	EuroScienceGateway
Antonio	Skarmeta	University of Murcia (Spain)	TITAN
Wolmar	Nyberg Åkerström	ELIXIR Sweden / NBIS, SciLifeLab, Uppsala University	EOSC-ENTRUST
Marc	Portier	VLIZ	FAIR-EASE

6.6.3 FAIR assessment and data objects (OAEG3 + TF2 + TF4)

First Name	Last Name	Organisation	Project(s)
Sheila	Izquieta-Rojano	BIOMA - University of Navarre	None
Ilona	Trtíková	CESNET	BeYond-COVID
Hervé	L'Hours	CESSDA/UK Data Service	FAIR-IMPACT
Juha	Lehtonen	CSC - IT Center for Science	EOSC-EDEN
Anca	Hienola	Finnish Meteorological Institute	OSCARS
Thierry	Carval	Ifremer	Blue-Cloud 2026
Matthias	Löbe	IMISE Universität Leipzig	None
Katerina	Slaninova	IT4Innovations, VSB - Technical University of Ostrava	None
Roxanne	Wyns	EOSC Association, KU Leuven	EOSC-EDEN
Olga	Bohuslavová	Masaryk University	None
Natalia	Manola	OpenAIRE AMKE	OSTrails
Ryan	O'Connor	RDA Association (RDA Europe)	RDA Tiger
Sylvia	Jeney	Swiss National Science Foundation	None
Chris	Schubert	TU Wien	None
Daniel	Garijo	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	OSTrails
Mark	Wilkinson	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	OSTrails
Munazah	Andrabi	University of Manchester	EOSC4Cancer

Jacques	Flores	Utrecht University	None
Klaus	Tochtermann	EOSC Association, ZBW - Leibniz Information Centre for Economics	None

6.6.4 User and Resource Environments: Trusted VREs and the EOSC Federation Model (OAEG4 + TF1 + TF3)

First Name	Last Name	Organisation	Project(s)
Fotis	Karayannis	ATHENA RC/Innov-Acts	STR-ESFRI
Julen	Torrens	BIOMA - University of Navarre	FAIR-IMPACT
Miroslav	Ruda	CESNET	EuroScienceGateway
Marie	Jossé	CNRS	FAIR-EASE
Samuel	Keuchkerian	CNRS	FAIR-EASE
Kaori	Otsu	CREAF	EOSC-Focus
Álvaro	López García	CSIC	AI4EOSC
Rene	Belso	DeiC	EOSC-ENTRUST
Nicola	Fiore	EGI Foundation	EOSC-Beyond
Sebastian	Luna-Valero	EGI Foundation	EuroScienceGateway
Diego	Scardaci	EGI Foundation	EOSC-Beyond
Peter	Maccallum	ELIXIR	EOSC-ENTRUST
Jean-Karim	Heriche	EMBL	None
Ignacio	Blanquer	EOSC Association, UPV	None
Stelios	Ninidakis	Hellenic Centre for Marine Research	FAIR-EASE
Juan	Gonzalez Garcia	IACS	BeYond-COVID
Lukas	Vojacek	IT4Innovations, VSB – Technical University of Ostrava	EOSC-ENTRUST
Patricia	Mergen	Meise Botanic Garden and Royal Museum for Central Africa	WorldFair

Pierre	Le Sidaner	Observatoire de Paris	OSCARS
Maja	Dolinar	OpenAIRE AMKE	EOSC-Beyond
Marcin	Plociennik	PSNC	AI4EOSC
Mark	van de Sanden	SURF/EUDAT	FAIRCORE4EOSC
Bjoern	Gruening	Universität Freiburg	EuroScienceGateway
Amanda	Calatrava Arroyo	Universitat Politècnica de València	AI4EOSC

6.6.5 Skills & engagement (OAE5)

First Name	Last Name	Organisation	Project(s)
Curtis	Sharma	4TU.ResearchData/TU Delft	Skills4EOSC
Athanasios	Vergoulis	ATHENA RC	GraspOS
Franciska	de Jong	CLARIN ERIC	EOSC-Focus, OSCARS
Iulianna	van der Lek	CLARIN ERIC	OSCARS
Anu	Märkälä	CSC	EOSC-EDEN, EOSC Focus
Jessica	Lindvall	ELIXIR, SciLifeLab, Stockholm University	None
Isabel	Caetano	EOSC Association	EOSC-Focus
Julia	Pries-Buchheit	EOSC-A/MIK	None
Magdalena	Szuflita-Żurawska	Gdańsk University of Technology	EOSC-FIDELIS
Celia	van Gelder	Health-RI	EOSC4Cancer
Victoria	Dominguez Del Angel	Inria	FAIRCORE4EOSC
Helen	Clare	Jisc	None
Clifford	Tatum	Leiden University	GraspOS
Natalia	Galica	NCN	EOSC-Focus
Liise	Lehtsalu	RDA Association (RDA Europe)	RDA Tiger

Ineke	Luijten	SciLifeLab	None
Patricia	Palagi	SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics	EOSC-FIDELIS
Hanna	Lindroos	SLU	None
Friederike	Schmidt-Tremmel	Trust-IT	OSCARS
Barbara	Sanchez	TU Wien	EOSC-Focus, Skills4EOSC
Fotis	Psomopoulos	CERTH	EVERSE
Eva	Méndez	uc3m-Skills4EOSC, CoARA	Skills4EOSC
Marialuisa	Lavitrano	EOSC Association, Università Milano Bicocca	None
Rene	Belso	DeiC, DK	EOSC-ENTRUST
Clara	Boavida	Iscte, Portugal	None

6.6.6 Open scholarly communication (OAEG6 + TF1 + TF2)

First Name	Last Name	Organisation	Project(s)
Elli	Papadopoulou	ATHENA RC	OSTrails
Nathalie	Fargier	CCSD	None
Leonidas	Pispiringas	OpenAIRE	CRAFT-OA
Tereza	Simova	OpenAIRE	None
Paolo	Manghi	OpenAIRE	OSTrails
Patrick	Ruch	Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics (ELIXIR-CH)	EVERSE
William	Illsley	Swedish National Data Service	Skills4EOSC
Ka Yee Suvini	Lai	TU Wien	EOSC-Focus
Ekaterina	Kutafina	University Hospital Cologne	None
Margo	Bargheer	University of Göttingen	CRAFT-OA

Elena	Giglia	University of Turin	CRAFT-OA
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6.6.7 Research software (OAE7)

First Name	Last Name	Organisation	Project(s)
Salvador	Capella Gutierrez	Barcelona Supercomputing Center	EOSC4Cancer
Fotis	Psomopoulos	INAB CERTH	EVERSE
Stefania	Amodeo	OpenAIRE AMKE	EVERSE
Morane	Gruenpeter	Software Heritage, INRIA	FAIRCORE4EOSC

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